

Paper 4

IoT Applications Vis-À-Vis Educational Systems & Management—An Overview

P. K. Paul¹, Ricardo Saavedra² & P. S. Aithal³

¹Executive Director (MCIS) & Asst. Prof. (IST), Department of CIS, & Information Scientist (Offg.),
Raiganj University, West Bengal, India

²Director & Chair, International Program, Azteca University, Mexico

³Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

Corresponding Author: pkpaul.infotech@gmail.com

Abstract

Information Systems and Technology is changed drastically in recent years with the initiation of various IT and Computing tools and among the emerging/ latest technologies few important are Cloud Computing, Big Data and Analytics, Human Computer Interaction, Usability Systems and Engineering, Internet of Things, etc. and among these IoT plays an important role in different sections and fields. Internet of Things (IoT) is important in different educational activities ranging from typical educational activities i.e., teaching and learning to educational planning and administration viz. special education, school security related activities, accommodation management, attendance management, remote classroom management. Apart from these in smart room-based learning also Internet of Things (IoT) is emerging and applicable. In the recent past, educational institutions in the developed countries are moving in designing and development of on campus educational systems smarter and advanced; and in this context, basic and latest Internet of Things (IoT) are worthy deal. This paper is review work and mainly deals with the IoT applications including foundation, the paper also highlights the applications of the Internet of Things (IoT) in basic education with emphasizing educational planning, administration, and management.

Keywords: Internet of Things, IoT, Information Systems, Smart Education, Digital Education, Information Technology Applications

Introduction

Internet of Things is a most important and valuable aspect, tool, method these days for wider information activities including collection, selection, organization, processing, management, and dissemination [1], [7]. This is the way for connecting different kinds of devices and products electronically using the internet. Here the use of the sensor plays a leading role in collecting data and information of various kinds of objective. Internet of things is growing rapidly in different countries and territories. The Internet of Things (IoT) is about different types of objects and here different kinds of built-in sensors are gathered for various kinds of data and connected networks are also playing a leading role. In IoT sensors role of automatic

adjustment play a leading role including different attributes such as heating and lighting. Moreover, IoT is also important in more efficient and smarter life enhancement. Furthermore, IoT devices bears different kind of IP address used in the collection and transforming data with more intelligent way and here it was less manual support based. Therefore, day by day IoT gain popularity in different sectors—

- Industries, Business and Commerce
- Education, Research and Training
- Government and Administration
- Healthcare and Medical Systems
- Transport, tourism and hospitality
- Manufacturing, Implementation and Development, etc.

Therefore, this trend is gaining day by day and every day there are lots of areas where IoT based systems are applicable. There are lot of areas where IoT can be applied and used in Education segments such as Special Education and Training, Physical Education and Training, Security in Educational Systems, Monitoring different educational institutions, observing and monitoring the institutions, physical and mental health, remote and online learning, etc [3], [14], [22].

Objective

The paper entitled ‘IoT Applications Vis-à-Vis Educational Systems & Management—*An Overview*’ is a theoretical one and therefore deals with the following aim and objective—

- To learn about the basics of the Internet of Things (IoT) including its foundations, framework briefly.
- To know about the basic and emerging features of the Internet of Things (IoT) including its allied areas.
- To dig out the role and potentiality of the Internet of Things (IoT) including its impact on education, training and development activities.
- To find out the present scenario of the Internet of Things (IoT) for different purposes of education and research.

IoT: Basics & Features

The term Internet of Things (IoT) was coined during the 1990s by entrepreneur Kevin Ashton; who was also the founder of the Auto-ID Center at MIT. He described the concept of the “Internet of Things” in a presentation in the year 1999 and thereafter many developments of the Internet of Things (IoT) is noted gradually—

- Internet of Things (IoT) is one of the emerging areas of Information Science and Technology and is also dedicated to internet related solutions.
- With the help of the Internet of Things (IoT) various services may be developed of using Internet support [5], [23].
- Various types of sectors such as healthcare, education, business and commerce, transportation, education and training, research and development, etc. is being developed and improved using IoT.

Fig: 1-The IoT Architecture at a glance

- In IoT, various other kinds of technologies like Cloud Computing, Big Data, Analytics are also associated to reach its actual goal (as depicted in Fig: 1).
- Internet of Things (IoT) is basically a sensor dependent service and also improving gradually for various alternative technologies.
- Internet of Things (IoT) is helpful in designing and developing various kind of Intelligent transport solutions which helps in managing traffic flows, also reduce fuel consumption as far as transportation segment is concerned.
- With the IoT, smart electric grids may be connected and it has improved smaller usage increments for wider benefits [6], [10], [20].
- Machine monitoring sensors help in mechanical process including the repairing of equipment and regional needs.
- As far as digital transformation is concerned IoT is helpful in developing the concept of smart cities including various advancement such as on run waste management, efficiency, etc.

- As far as home security is concerned IoT is able in managing remote control based systems in home management including opening and closing of windows, as per need.

IoT Applications in Education, Teaching and Learning

Internet of Things (IoT) is applicable in wide range of areas and sectors for the purpose of better information management but as far as education, teaching and learning is concerned it is applicable in a wide range of areas. As far as stakeholders are concerned the following may be considered as main stakeholders—

Student

With the help of IoT different kinds of pupils, students, trainees, learners will get the benefits in different kinds of activities such as personalized learning as per the study of user behavior study, learning from anywhere and anytime process, growth in student engagement in the learning and development process. More and further improved learning results of the students.

Instructor and Teachers

The IoT based systems and techniques help in various benefits to the teachers, professors, instructors and trainers such as developing the teaching plan more personalized way, maintaining and developing better attendance systems, use of digital tools in explaining new material provides the way to experimentalism with educating process and so on [4], [11].

Administration & Management

Now if we look at another important stakeholder of the education segment that is administrators and management, and that also needs the support of the administrators and management. IoT based system is helpful in proper management of principal, director, dean, chancellor, provost, etc. It is helpful in healthy monitoring of HVAC system, lighting, locks, etc including proper and healthy increase of the security, proper and enhanced systems of LMS content can be modified [8], [21].

Fig:2 itself depicted the overall beneficiaries of the Internet of Things (IoT) as far as Education, Teaching, and Research segment is concerned, Fig: 3 showing the major kind of stakeholders of IoT in education.

Fig: 2-The basic beneficiaries of IoT applications in Education

In Smart and Dedicated Class Room

As far as a smart and dedicated classroom environment is concerned, the Internet of Things (IoT) plays a leading role in the contemporary scenario. Today most of the students are enjoy smart and whiteboards and projects instead of blackboard. Smart board gives more interaction, fun, and easy to understand the environment. In a smart board many concepts may be taught instantly, it helps in attending confusion among the students. Different students may have different types of confusion and perception and here using the Internet of Things (IoT) the situation may be solved. The IoT enabled smartboard is helpful in the exchange of information simple, interesting, and interactive. With smartboards, teachers can offer effective teaching, complex theory, and formulae easily. Furthermore, as far as smart and dedicated classroom is concerned it gives following—

- In the present context Virtual reality is gaining a lot and as far as education, training, and research are concerned this trend is also growing and here the Internet of Things (IoT) is applicable due to outstanding requirements.
- Internet of Things (IoT) is able in counting and percept various situations like when the class is too tired or required a recess, etc [9], [13].
- Whiteboard and the smartboard can record the class, teacher's voice and therefore able in managing homework, assignment, etc.

Fig: 3-Major Stakeholders of IoT applications

In Concentration of Attendance

Internet of Things (IoT) is more perfectly useful in proper attendance of the students, teachers, staff of the concerned educational institute. Anytime based on requirement IoT based system may generate data and pull out actual and required data [16], [17]. In many contexts, details of the attendance may be taken using the Internet of Things (IoT) and these may be useful in allowing students in appearing examinations, giving marks, and credit. Furthermore, in the Internet of Things (IoT) based system, it may be with less error or without any error. Furthermore, attendance of the staff also important for providing salary as per their duties and attendance, IoT may be considered as valuable and important. Calculating student attendance and generating regularity, punctuality, and personality reports generation becomes too easy using the Internet of Things (IoT) based systems. The amount of time spends in an institute in a specified timeframe become also possible to measure perfectly using Internet of Things (IoT). Additionally, a quick electronic message may be sent to the parents or other stakeholders [2], [12].

In Safety and Surveillances

Safety and surveillance are very much important in educational systems and as far as the Internet of Things (IoT) application is concerned it could be considered as an important one. In this regard following may be applicable—

- Emergency Indicators
- Audio Enhancer
- Wi-fi clocks

- Hearing impaired notifications, etc.

In the case of an electronic short circuit, the IoT based sensor may immediately notify/alert for the needful. Real-time data can be generated using electronic systems and in this regard Internet of Things (IoT) is important. In earthquakes, sudden and fatal weather changes IoT sensors and meters can be considered as important.

In Disability Management

Internet of Things (IoT) is helpful in proper disability management as far as modern time is concerned. The modern technological designs, learning new things, and performing systems make easier orientation towards disability management. There are many students who are suffering from the challenges to the sense of hearing; and here Internet of Things (IoT) system may be connected for generating verbal speech, translated from sign language, and so on. IoT devices are suitable for proper educational assistance to disabled children in many contexts.

In Mobile Applications and Tablets

The Internet of Things (IoT) based systems are able in gathering data from multiple devices and electronics products. Once it was treated as a bad having among the children regarding the uses of electronic products, tools and gadgets; but now it becomes an important necessity. Therefore, Internet of Things (IoT) based system may be used in gathering data from such devices in a different context. The sensors of the IoT are dedicated to collecting data and thereafter is automatically suggests the particular academic topics of interest to the students and other stakeholders. And in this regard Smartphones, tablets, and other electronic devices have becomes worthy [7], [15].

In Foreign Language Education

As far as teaching a foreign language is concerned, there are certain issues and problems and many of such problems may be solved using online systems and very particularly modern Internet of Things (IoT) based tools and systems. Real-time feedback is important in learning and in this context Internet of Things (IoT) become worthy and important. The real-time feedback from native is become easy using IoT. In foreign language, simulation environments real-time feedback to the students become most valuable and worthy.

In Online and Digital Education

As far as Online and Digital Education is concerned the Internet of Things (IoT) is helpful in developing the system in many ways. The class, feedback systems, content generation, and

development become effective with IoT based systems. Furthermore, it also helps in managing proper and healthy online and digital education with proper report generation [10], [19].

Smart way forward: The Internet of Things (IoT) is important and worthy in managing healthy and developed education systems including potential future IoT applications in education, it also processes of integrating educational environments.

Challenges of IoT in Education

Though there are many benefits of Internet of Things (IoT) in education, teaching and learning but there are certain challenges in this implementing Internet of Things (IoT) in the education systems; and we may need to overcome the certain issues such as—

Implementation Cost—

There are certain issues in implementing the Internet of Things (IoT) in the education segment and among these important is implementation cost. Though it may be nominal for the developed countries but may be considered as an important issue in developing and undeveloped nations. The costs are majorly based on the hardware, software, infrastructure, devices, and skill development to entire stakeholders of the education systems. In many contexts licensing of hardware and software become an important issue.

Matter of Ethics—

Ethics is another important factor that must be considered as valuable in respect of Internet of Things (IoT) implementation in the education segment. It is important to design the system in such a way so that it could be helpful in maintaining ethics. There are many aspects of the education system such as preventing cheating, plagiarism, academic dishonesty, etc. and in this respect Internet of Things (IoT) system needs to be more advanced and healthier [18], [23].

Bad and lack Data Infrastructure—

Infrastructure related to the Data and Information is very important and therefore the issues related to this must need to entertain in order to develop healthy systems. Reliable computer tools and systems must be provided.

Security, Privacy, and Information Assurance—

Many times, the Internet of Things (IoT) based systems may be undertaken by a third party and in this context, the issues related to security must be entertained.

Interest and Policy Formulation—

As far as the Internet of Things (IoT) in education system is concerned one of the major challenges is interest and proper policy formulation in respect of developments of the systems in the educational institutions. Therefore, proper policy is required from the part of educational institutions, government bodies, ministries, educational agencies, etc.

Conclusion

Technology is in many ways changing the entire education system and leads to an improved educational system and smarter education. All such integration is helpful to the staff, students, teachers, etc for teaching services. IoT solutions for education create healthy, interactive, and developed education systems in developed countries; though the question of equality is now equally distributed to the disabled students as well using IoT. The data generation of various types many ways now lies on IoT including complex formulas, concepts, and theories possibility. Classroom studies now become important and interesting. The IoT devices ultimately uplift the global society as a whole due to their credit in physical or traditional mode of educational systems and emerging mode of education system such as online education, blended learning, etc. IoT in education becomes worthy to the teachers, students, administrators, and all kinds of stakeholders.

Reference

- [30] Abbasy, M. B., & Quesada, E. V. (2017). Predictable influence of IoT (Internet of Things) in the higher education. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 7(12), 914-920.
- [31] Adamuthe, A. C., Salunkhe, V. D., Patil, S. H., & Thampi, G. T. (2015). Cloud Computing– A market Perspective and Research Directions. *International Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science (IJITCS)*, 7(10), 42-53.
- [32] Ahmadvand, A. M., Nasiri, H., NasrollahiNia, F., & Mahjoubian, A. (2019). Internet of Things; A system for improving the higher education system. *Technology of Education Journal (TEJ)*, 14(1), 157-168.
- [33] Aldowah, H., Rehman, S. U., Ghazal, S., & Umar, I. N. (2017, September). Internet of Things in higher education: a study on future learning. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 892, No. 1, p. 012017). IOP Publishing.
- [34] Al-Emran, M., Malik, S. I., & Al-Kabi, M. N. (2020). A survey of internet of things (IoT) in education: opportunities and challenges. *Toward social internet of things (SIoT): Enabling technologies, architectures and applications*, 197-209.
- [35] Al-Mamary, Y. H., Shamsuddin, A., & Abdul Hamid, N. A. (2014). The meaning of management information systems and its role in telecommunication companies in Yemen. *American Journal of Software Engineering*, 2(2), 22-25.
- [36] Bayani, M., Leiton, K., & Loaiza, M. (2017). Internet of things (IoT) advantages on e-learning in the smart cities. *International Journal of Development Research*, 7(12), 17747-17753.

- [37] Bhatt, J., & Bhatt, A. (2017). IoT techniques to nurture education industry: scope & opportunities. *International Journal On Emerging Technologies*. Uttarakhand, India, 128-132.
- [38] Charmonman, S., Mongkhonvanit, P., Dieu, V. N., & Linden, N. (2015). Applications of internet of things in e-learning. *International Journal of the Computer, the Internet and Management*, 23(3), 1-4.
- [39] Chweya, R., Ibrahim, O., & Nilashi, M. (2019). IoT in Higher Learning Institutions: Opportunities and Challenges. *Journal of Soft Computing and Decision Support Systems*, 6(6), 1-8.
- [40] Chweya, R., Ajibade, S. S. M., Buba, A. K., & Samuel, M. (2020). IoT and Big Data Technologies: Opportunities and Challenges for Higher Learning. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, 9 (2), 909, 913.
- [41] Fernández-Caramés, T. M., & Fraga-Lamas, P. (2020). Teaching and learning iot cybersecurity and vulnerability assessment with shodan through practical use cases. *Sensors*, 20(11), 3048.
- [42] Ilieva, G., & Yankova, T. (2020). IoT in Distance Learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *IoT in Distance Learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic*, 9(4), 1669-1674.
- [43] McRae, L., Ellis, K., & Kent, M. (2018). Internet of things (IoT): education and technology. *Relatsh. between Educ. Technol. students with Disabil. Leanne, Res*, 1-37.
- [44] Pai, S. S. (2017). IOT Application in Education. *International Journal for Advance Research and Development*, 2(6), 20-24.
- [45] Paul, P.K., A. Bhuimali, P.S. Aithal, R. Rajesh and Vennila H (2019), Internet of Things (IoT): Towards an Emerging Area—A Study. In *Digital Technology, Automation and Advanced Communication Systems/ ISBN: 978-93-88879-25-5* edited by P.K. Paul et al., New Delhi Publishers, New Delhi, India.
- [46] Paul, P. K., Solanki, V. K., & Kumar, R. (2020). An Analytical Approach from Cloud Computing Data Intensive Environment to Internet of Things in Academic Potentialities. In *Principles of Internet of Things (IoT) Ecosystem: Insight Paradigm* (pp. 363-381). Springer, Cham.
- [47] Paul, P.K., R.R.Sinha, P.S. Aithal, R. Saavedra, B. Aremu, S. Mewada (2020). Internet of Things (IoT) and Smart Agriculture: With Reference to Applications and Emerging Concern. *Asian Journal of Electrical Sciences*, 9(1), 37-44
- [48] Paul, P.K., Saavedra, R., Aithal, P.S., Sinha, R.R. and Aremu, B. (2020). Agro Informatics Vis-à-Vis Internet of Things (IoT) Integration & Potentialities—*An Analysis*. *Agro Economist - An International Journal*, 7(1), 13-20.
- [49] Paul, P. K. (2021). Agricultural Informatics vis-à-vis Internet of Things (IoT): The Scenario, Applications and Academic Aspects—International Trend & Indian Possibilities. *Agricultural Informatics: Automation Using the IoT and Machine Learning*, 35-65.
- [50] Pervez, S., ur Rehman, S., & Alandjani, G. (2018). Role of internet of things (iot) in higher education. In *In 4th International Conference on Advances in Education and Social Sciences* (pp. 792-800).

- [51] Soni, V. D. (2019). IOT connected with e-learning. *Vishal Dineshkumar Soni.(2019). IOT connected with e-learning. International Journal on Integrated Education, 2(5), 273-277.*
- [52] Srivastava, M., Saurabh, P., & Verma, B. (2019). IOT for Capturing Information and Providing Assessment Framework for Higher Educational. *Soft Computing for Problem Solving: SocProS 2018, Volume 2, 1057, 249.*
